

Pulmonary Hypertension and Obstructive Sleep Apnea: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a disorder process affecting recurrent pharyngeal collapse during sleep, leading to apneic attacks. Clinically, manifestations can include snoring, sudden awakening with a choking-like sensation, excessive somnolence, non-restorative sleep, difficulty in initiation or maintenance of sleep, and fatigue. It leads to ineffective gas exchange, subsequently causing different cardiovascular, metabolic, and neurocognitive events. Recent studies have showed that OSA has been underestimated and underdiagnosed, especially in female cases. OSA is correlated with WHO (World Health Organization) class III pulmonary hypertension (PH) or PH because of lung disease. PH is an important complication of OSA and seems to involve roughly 20% of patients with OSA. The mechanism of PH in OSA can be associated with pulmonary artery vasoconstriction and remodeling. Cases with OSA who suffer from PH are susceptible to worse cardiovascular and pulmonary disorders. Therefore, in this review of the literature, we investigated the association between OSA and PH.

Keywords: Diagnosis, obstructive sleep apnea, pulmonary hypertension, treatment.

Introduction

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is known by recurrent pharyngeal collapse during sleep. Complete collapse of the pharynx can lead to apnea, whereas partial collapse causes hypopnea (1). OSA is associated with abnormalities such as gas exchange, leading to oxygen desaturation, hypercapnia, and sleep disturbances, which have pivotal roles in the other cardiovascular, metabolic, and neurocognitive disorders. OSA is a very common disorder diagnosed in many cases and is commonly underdiagnosed and undertreated (2). Many cases remain unaware of their underlying status and as such cannot receive appropriate treatments. Other barriers towards developing treatment for OSA include the stigma related to snoring, and access to polysomnography (especially in remote countries and in the developing world). Primary care doctors may not pursue early diagnosis of OSA, especially if cases do not endorse subjective sleepiness and the classic manifestation of a high body mass index (BMI) (3). This perception of the characteristic of the typical case with OSA remains despite findings on the contrary. For example, up to 50% of subjects with OSA are not obese and 25% of cases with moderate OSA do not present with any form of sleepiness. Cases who are particularly at risk of having OSA include those who show increased daytime sleepiness and as a result can be drowsy driving an automobile or may experience work-related events due to fatigue, cognitive problems related to fatigue, hypertension, nasopharyngeal narrowing, and pulmonary hypertension (PH) (3, 4). Cases suffering from OSA commonly have snoring, episodes of apneas, sudden awakening with a choking-like sensation, excessive somnolence, non-restorative sleep, difficulty in initiating or continuing sleep, fatigue, nocturia, memory dysfunction, and a morning headache. Chronic, loud snoring, increased BMI, and a neck size of >17 inches in men and >16 inches in women are correlated with a higher risk of OSA. OSA can occur due to the several factors including decrease in the strength of the pharyngeal dilators, the negative inspiratory pressure produced by the diaphragm, and disorders within the upper airway anatomy, with usual regions of obstruction located in the pharynx. Airway failure can be seen when patients with OSA sleep on their back and the base of the tongue adheres to both the posterior pharyngeal wall and the soft palate. An enlarged soft palate, a large tongue, an edematous uvula, redundant pharyngeal mucosal, and large tonsils are the most important risk factors for snoring and OSA (5, 6). OSA is correlated with WHO (World Health Organization) class III PH or PH due to lung disease. PH is an important complication of OSA and seems to be seen in approximately 20% of cases with OSA, but the range is anywhere from 17% to 70% in the studies. There are several indicators that increase the risk of susceptibility to PH and OSA, such as older age, obesity, left-sided heart disease, parenchymal lung disease, and nocturnal desaturation. The level of the pulmonary artery pressure associates with the severity of OSA (7). Therefore, in this review of the literature, we investigated the association between OSA and PH.

Epidemiology

A major study investigating the prevalence of OSA was the 1993 Wisconsin Sleep Cohort report, which revealed that OSA is common in roughly 4% of men and 2% of women among the middle-aged people and increases with age. The prevalence seems to range from 28% to 72% in elderly men and 20% to 54% in elderly women (8). These reports are rough estimates and seem to be falsely low given how often OSA is undetected. Men have been shown to be approximately three times more possible to have OSA; however, they are nine times more possible to be referred for polysomnography, which proposes that

the diagnosis of OSA may be underestimated in women. The prevalence of obesity in the United States is increasing at a rapid rate. In 2017 -2018, an estimated 42.4% of U.S. adult cases were obese as known as a BMI of ≥ 30 (8, 9). Obesity is a risk factor for PH independent of the existence of OSA and can more complicate the manifestation of OSA. When PH occurs secondary to OSA, the manifestations may not be as clearly known due to obesity and lack of physical function. More complicating the picture, OSA is an independent risk factor for health disorders such as myocardial ischemia, systemic hypertension, congestive heart failure, arrhythmias, and sudden cardiac death. Therefore, PH manifestations can be overseen in lieu of cardiovascular complications that take precedence (9, 10). Cases who are obese are also susceptible to having obesity hypoventilation syndrome (OHS). OHS cases have a prevalence 59% more than of PH in OSA than having OSA alone, which is possibly related to increased hypercapnic effects. When weight loss treatments are performed, OSA severity is decreased (9-11).

Underlying Mechanisms

The mechanisms of PH in OSA are related to intermittent hypoxia, hypercapnia, acidosis, sympathetic hyperactivity, negative pleural pressure, and endothelial dysfunction. The end outcome is pulmonary artery vasoconstriction and remodeling. The pathophysiology behind PH and hypoxia seems to be related to the decrease of duration of a hypoxic state. Cases with OSA show cyclical events of oxygen desaturation that last from 10 to more than 40 seconds each hour subsequent to arousal and either partial or complete recovery of oxygen saturation (9, 12, 13). The events of hypoxia and hypercapnia in OSA lead to a series of pulmonary arterial vasoconstriction and remodeling. While the exact pathophysiology is unknown, levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), known for vasodilatory effects, are decreased in acute hypoxia states. This mechanism leads to higher pulmonary arterial pressures. Settings of chronic hypoxia seem to lead to vascular remodeling. The etiology of this mechanism is related to endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) suppression, which leads to reduced levels of nitric oxide (NO), a vasodilator (12, 14). Vasoactive triggers, such as endothelin-1 and NO, are at lower levels in OSA cases. Endothelin-1 is a potent vasoconstrictor that is synthesized by the endothelium and is commonly increased in cases with chronic intermittent hypoxia, as demonstrated in animal investigations, by binding to increased levels of ET A (endothelin A) receptors on the pulmonary artery. Animal investigations showed that rats exposed to chronic intermittent hypoxia also had impaired endothelium, resulting in less endothelium-dependent vasodilation. Similar conditions are seen with NO in the setting of chronic intermittent hypoxia with inhibition of eNOS and impaired vasodilation of the endothelium, initiated by NF- κ B (nuclear factor kappa B) process (9, 15, 16). Certain anti-inflammatory mediators, such as adiponectin, are reduced in obesity and OSA, a possible association between conditions of pulmonary artery hypertension in OSA cases. Adiponectin has a role in vasodilation of the pulmonary vessels. When levels are reduced, resultant systemic hypertension develops. Low level of adiponectin is also correlated with impaired vasoreactivity, which can more affect pulmonary vessels. Given the multifactorial mechanism between obesity and OSA, it is not interesting that OHS would be correlated with PH as well. OHS seems to be associated with PH through a series of pathways including diurnal hypoxemia, hypercapnia, and acidosis. The degree of obesity present seems to change thoracic pressure variations in the respiratory cycle related to upper airway resistance. The resultant endothelial

impairment, arterial wall thickening, and fibrosis result in pulmonary artery remodeling and pulmonary artery hypertension (10, 12, 15, 17).

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of OSA is initially performed based on polysomnographic findings seen in a sleep laboratory. Home polysomnography is a viable choice for cases who cannot perform an overnight laboratory test, albeit it is less accurate and should not be used in cases with cardiovascular, pulmonary, or neurologic disorders. Although the American Academy of Sleep Medicine proposes that signs and symptoms of OSA should be evaluated in every case, the U.S. Preventive Services Task Force has no suggestion for general evaluation (18). Risk factors that may need evaluation in the primary setting include subjects aged 40 to 70 years, commercial motor vehicle operators, positive family past history, BMI > 35, postmenopausal women not on hormonal treatment, retrognathia, and as a preoperative evaluation for bariatric surgery. Initial evaluation of OSA commonly includes evaluation questionnaires such as the STOP-Bang questionnaire and the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS). Despite the common use of ESS in primary care and as a subjective endpoint in clinical investigation, its performance pales in comparison to STOP-BANG with a sensitivity of only 39% versus 87%, respectively. ESS only takes into account sleepiness, a cardinal sign of OSA, but one that is hardly universal in all cases regardless of the severity of disease, whereas STOP-BANG includes different subjective and objective items predictive of OSA, including observed apnea, neck circumference, age, and gender (19). During polysomnography, cases are assessed for episodes of apnea and hypopnea. Apnea is characterized as a complete obstruction of airflow for more than 10 seconds. Hypopnea, on the other hand, is known as a partial obstruction of airflow evaluated by an oxygen desaturation of at least 3% or by arousals from sleep, each lasting more than 10 seconds. These apneic and hypopneic episodes are summed and divided by total hours of sleep to find the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) (20, 21). Mild OSA has an AHI of 5-15 and is known by involuntary somnolence during functions that demand little attention, including watching television or reading. Moderate OSA has an AHI of 15-30 and makes involuntary sleepiness during activities that need some attention, including meetings or speaking. Severe OSA has an AHI of >30 and includes involuntary somnolence during activities that demand an increased attention such as talking or driving. PH has several mechanisms, including OSA (WHO group III). Although AHI does not determine who will develop PH, those that do develop PH tend to have worse cardiovascular and pulmonary functions if the AHI is within the moderate-to-severe range versus mild. The American College of Chest Physicians (ACCP) suggests evaluation for sleep-disordered breathing in cases shown to have pulmonary arterial hypertension and subsequent polysomnography if OSA is suspected as the pathophysiology (22, 23). However, there exist no formal instructions for the evaluation of PH in cases who have the diagnosis of OSA. Evaluation for PH of any etiology commonly involves 2D echocardiography with Doppler flow investigations, which is also effective in excluding cardiac disease that may be contributory to elevated pulmonary pressure (24, 25). Evidence of PH can also be gleaned from electrocardiogram (ECG) strips approving signs of right ventricular hypertrophy (right axis deviation, tall right precordial R waves) as persistent pulmonary arterial hypertension subsequently results in cor pulmonale. Suggestive ECG results should prompt echocardiographic assessment in these cases (26-28). Nonetheless, the gold standard for identifying PH is based on right heart catheterization with current thresholds known as a

pulmonary artery pressure higher than 25 mmHg at rest or higher than 30 mmHg with exertion. Although these investigations are invasive, they may be of more effective in obese cases versus echocardiography due to body habitus obscuring appropriate interpretation. Likewise, right cardiac catheterization is crucial to exclude left heart causes of PH for which vasodilatory treatments such as NO, adenosine, epoprostenol, or nitroprusside would be contraindicated. Other investigations that should be carried out on cases with OSA and/or PH include common biochemical, hematologic, and immunologic assessments, thyroid function evaluations, pulmonary function studies, chest imaging, arterial blood gases, and ventilation-perfusions scans to exclude any other potentially reversible aspects of disease (2, 23).

Treatment

OSA has been treated by several different treatments over the years including CPAP (continuous positive airway pressure), surgical procedures, medical therapies, and exogenous devices. The goal is commonly directed at decreasing the number of apneic and hypopneic events, reducing nocturnal arousals, and ameliorating arterial oxyhemoglobin saturation. CPAP is known as the first line and the gold standard therapy for OSA (29, 30). When used properly, CPAP reduces daytime sleepiness, makes sleep architecture normal, and improves morbidity and mortality related to OSA, which may include the deleterious effects of PH. Optimal intervention is described as 4 to 6 hours per night; however, many cases find it impossible to adhere to this due to comfort, convenience, noise, claustrophobia, and cost. The rate of adherence has been commonly low over the last 20 years despite behavioral actions and patient coaching. CPAP has long been the intervention of choice for OSA as it maintains the airway open during sleep; however, improvement in PH has not been clearly demonstrated (18). Two investigations showed the association between CPAP treatment and PH in cases without underlying pulmonary or cardiac disease and showed that pulmonary artery pressure effectively was reduced after four 16 weeks of treatment. Arias et al. (31) used a placebo control group and more extensive exclusion criteria, whereas Sajkov et al. (32) did not use them. Nevertheless, patient basic characteristics and ultimate results were similar between each study. CPAP treatment was shown to help maintain normal serum level of vasoactive factors, affecting pulmonary vascular tone and vascular smooth muscle proliferation. The effect on left ventricular afterload and diastolic relaxation may be the factor that is easily reversed following three months of treatment, as seen in these investigations. However, more investigations of the reversibility of pulmonary structural alterations after a more prolonged course of intervention is warranted, especially in OSA patients with concurrent PH. Although CPAP treatment is approved, compliance rates are very low (30-60%), which makes developing alternative interventions for OSA and thus PH imperative. A trial overdrive pacing (A OP) in which a pacemaker is set to 15 beats per minute above a patient's baseline nocturnal heart rate was one such alternative noted since there was a reported decrease in breathing diseases after implantation. The prospective investigation by Garrigue et al. (33) showed that A OP in cases who had received pacemakers for the treatment of symptomatic sinus bradycardia and who also had sleep apnea had a considerable decrease in their hypopnea index (the total number of episodes of hypopnea divided by the number of hours of sleep), lower arousal, and higher arterial oxyhemoglobin saturation. These results suggest an alternative intervention for cases who already have a pacemaker in place for bradycardia and also occur to suffer from continued sleep

apnea after CPAP failure. This investigation included cases with both central sleep apnea and OSA and showed amelioration in indices for both. In terms of central sleep apnea, A OP may reduce periodic alterations in heart rate by reducing vagal tone reaction to hypoxemia, hypercapnia, bradycardia, and reduced blood pressure, resulting in an increase in cardiac output and reduction of pulmonary congestion. Less changes in a patient's heart rate was correlated with a decreased number of apneic events. A process for improved indices in OSA was not reported in this investigation. Three randomized controlled trials used this same intervention but only included cases with OSA rather than central or mixed sleep apnea. In stark contrast to the investigation by Garrigue et al. (33), none of the three trials showed considerable improvement in AHI, respiratory indices, or subjective sleep quality factors. In addition to excluding cases with other sleep apnea syndromes, Simantirakis et al. (34) also excluded any case with clinical left ventricular systolic dysfunction and postulated that cases with mild left ventricular ejection dysfunction may have revealed benefits to A OP due to better cardiac activity and decrease in periodic breathing. Patient age in this investigation was also younger than the others, with a mean of 60 ± 11 years in comparison with mean ages of 69 ± 9 , 71 ± 10 , and 74 ± 6.6 years, more representing a healthier cohort overall. These cases were randomly divided to standard CPAP versus A OP treatment for one month with crossover after the initial treatment. Although A OP did not have a significant role in OSA, this investigation did approve that CPAP had a significant effect on AHI, respiratory indices, and ESS, more corroborating that CPAP is the superior intervention when patient compliance is optimal(35). Two other studies included cases with left ventricular heart failure in their randomized trial, with the latter adopting this as an inclusion criterion. Another study reported that A OP had a mild effect on respiratory disorders in this particular subset but could not approve any more benefit of A OP intervention in terms of patency or sleep function. Taken together, it is thought that A OP is not an appropriate alternative to CPAP in cases with obstructive type sleep apnea but may indeed suggest benefit for those with central or mixed apneas (29, 35). Moreover, A OP will possibly not reveal improvement in OSA cases with concomitant or resultant PH due to lack of efficacy in otherwise healthy OSA cases, although this factor has not been effectively investigated. Since OSA is largely due to nocturnal anatomic impairment of airflow, several surgical procedures have been used to address the source of obstruction, including uvulopalatopharyngoplasty (UPPP), tonsillectomy, tracheostomy, radiofrequency ablation of tissue, and advancement and change of skeletal and soft tissue anatomies (36). The most frequent surgical intervention used in the treatment of OSA is UPPP since it is less invasive and relatively well tolerated. This intervention needs the removal of excess tissue of the oral and nasopharyngeal mucosa and submucosa, shortening of the uvula, and sparing of the palatoglossal and palatopharyngeal muscles. In a recent investigation, the main aim was to assess if there was an effective enlargement of the upper airway due to UPPP and whether this would lead to improved AHI (36). Although the majority of the cases in the investigation were known poor responders pursuant to inappropriate improvement in AHI, those who did herald a good response had an enhancement in the cross-sectional area of the oropharynx after surgical procedure. Those who responded poorly to UPPP showed an increased width of the soft palate, which may be contributory to less than optimal response. Another investigation carried out to show the long-term response of this procedure (UPPP alone and UPPP plus tonsillectomy) over a period that ranged over about six years (37). The findings of this investigation revealed considerable improvement in snoring but varied responses to other sleep quality factors such as excessive daytime sleepiness and oxygen desaturation. However, when combined with

tonsillectomy, measurements of nocturnal desaturation showed improvement that may correlate with an even more increased cross-sectional area of the oropharynx. As stated in previous sections, elevated cross-sectional area is associated with a better response; nevertheless, not all cases who received more tonsillectomy in this investigation were noted to have a good response. Procedures such as UPPP may primarily be effective and increase quality of life versus CPAP treatment; however, recurrence of excessive daytime sleepiness was evident in this study after six months postoperatively and at long-term follow-up, which may show decreased benefit after an extended post-surgical period (37, 38). UPPP remains effective in only around 20% of cases, and detecting “good responders” pre-operatively has been difficult to discern thus far. A recent investigation assessed whether there was a difference in UPPP results based on patients’ pre-operative positional dependency. Positional dependency is attributed to an OSA case when signs and symptoms are more pronounced in the supine position compared to lateral positioning (approved by a difference in supine AHI > 2 times that of the lateral position). In this regard, positional independence is evident with more severe OSA, and based on this investigation, this was the population that benefitted the most from UPPP treatment (39). An improvement in AHI indices was reported in both position-dependent and position-independent cases; however, the change was more considerable in the position-independent cohort in both the supine and lateral positions, with the main proportion of these cases actually becoming position-dependent after procedure. Therefore, evaluating positional dependency pre-operatively could serve as a beneficial selection tool to stratify those most susceptible to reap the benefits of UPPP and potentially other surgical interventions for OSA. Besides UPPP, other surgical procedures included in this study are radiofrequency ablation of obstructing tissue, and upper airway stimulation system implants. Radiofrequency ablation can be directed towards the tongue, turbinates, or soft palate, and commonly does not need general anesthesia (40). However, the drawback of this kind of procedure is that multiple sessions may be required before amelioration of AHI and subjective sleep efficiency factors could be found. An investigation used an electrode to deliver temperature-controlled radiofrequency to decrease the volumetric mass of palatal submucosa in 22 non-randomized cases with sleep-disordered breathing and revealed a considerable improvement in esophageal pressures, sleep efficiency, snoring, and ESSs with a mean of 3.6 ± 1.2 treatment sessions (41). In contrast, no considerable improvement in OSA factors was detected in a randomized controlled trial. Suggestion for radiofrequency ablation as an alternative warrants more assessment but may continue to serve as an adjunct to standard intervention. While the previous surgical treatments stated serve to permanently reduce the effective mass of tissue periodically blocking the oropharynx in OSA, upper airway stimulation system implants preserve the anatomic structure of the oropharynx and instead delivers an impulse to mechanically decrease obstruction (38). While OSA is commonly known by apnea and hypopnea caused by soft palate collapse, hypoactivation of the genioglossus muscle is also associated with reduced patency of the airway as relaxation of the muscle causes the tongue to retract posteriorly and makes obstruction. Another study assessed the efficacy of hypoglossal nerve stimulation in correcting the periodic obstruction caused by tongue base displacement by way of an implantable electrode wrapped around the hypoglossal nerve. Of the 126 cases who had undergone procedure, only 46 had a good response and were then divided to receive treatment maintenance or treatment withdrawal (42). During this process, no considerable difference between AHI was found, leading researchers to conclude that improvement in overall AHI score was a result of the year-long hypoglossal nerve stimulation rather than variability in AHI score. This investigation was funded and partially

conducted by Inspire Medical Systems. Less invasive treatment interventions that also target tongue-based obstruction include mandibular advancement splints and tongue stabilizing devices. Both interventions revealed a significant decrease in AHI and subjective sleep factors in an investigation, but they may have subsequent issues with compliance as observed in CPAP since it needs the operator to use an intra-oral device during sleep (43).

Conclusions

Novel therapies for OSA are currently being assessed in an effort to find an effective choice that both decreases the deleterious effects of this disease and provides a promising intervention to increase patient satisfaction and adherence. Results of previous studies have culminated in the institution of CPAP as the first-line option for sleep apnea and has resulted in a number of investigations evaluating its concurrent therapeutic roles in PH. Investigations of this nature are severely lacking for alternative therapeutic interventions in the treatment of OSA. The challenge remains in identifying and approving a viable alternative to CPAP that is effective in a sizable proportion of those treated and investigating its roles in PH. Interestingly, pulmonary disease has served as exclusionary criteria for many investigations, but moving forward we think that it would be effective to include a cohort of OSA cases with PH in the study of alternative treatment choices for OSA. Associations may even be detected that stratifies “good” and “poor” responders to novel therapies by initial presence or absence of PH. PH remains a devastating outcome of the constellation of disease pathologies initiating from OSA. Since many cases are involved by OSA are underdiagnosed and undertreated, so too may be different concurrent patients with PH. Physicians require to continue to consider the strong correlation between OSA and underlying PH when diagnosing and treating cases with either disease processes.

Declarations

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Author Contribution

Fatemeh Taheri: Study design, review of literature, writing draft of study.

Amin Basharkhah: Study design, review of literature, writing draft of study.

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Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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